

Certain properties of ω - Q -fuzzy subrings

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we define the ω - Q -fuzzy subring and discussed various fundamental aspects of ω - Q -fuzzy subrings. We introduce the concept of ω - Q -level subset of this new fuzzy set and prove that ω - Q -level subset of ω - Q -fuzzy subring form a ring. We define ω - Q -fuzzy ideal and show that set of all ω - Q -fuzzy cosets form a ring. Moreover, we investigate the properties of homomorphic image of ω - Q -fuzzy subring.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In mathematics, ring theory is one of the most important part of abstract algebra. In algebra, ring theory studies the algebraic structures of rings. Rings algebraic structure is a framework in which addition and multiplication are well defined with some more properties.

The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by Zadeh [1] in 1965. Many mathematician have applied various hybrid models of fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets to several algebraic structure such as group theory [2, 3], non-associative ring [4, 5], time series [6, 7] and decision making [8]. Rosenfeld [9] commenced the idea of fuzzy subgroups in 1971. The fuzzy subrings were initiated by Liu [10] Dixit et al. [11] described the notion of level subgroup in 1990. The idea of anti-fuzzy subgroups was invented by Biswas [12]. Gupta [13] defined many classical t -operators in 1991. Solairaju and Nagarajan [14] explored a new structure and construction of Q -fuzzy groups in 2009. Muthuraj et al. [15] proposed the study of lower level subsets of anti-QFS in 2010. The concept of Q -fuzzy normal subgroups and Q -fuzzy normalizer were established by Priya et al. [16] in 2013. Sither Selvam et al. [17] used the Biswas work to modify the idea of anti-QFNS in 2014. Alsarahead and Ahmed [18-20] commenced new concept of complex fuzzy subring, complex fuzzy subgroup and complex fuzzy soft subgroups in 2017. Makaba and Murali [21] discussed fuzzy subgroups of finite groups. Rasuli [22] discussed Q -fuzzy subring with respect to t -norm in 2018. The Q -fuzzy subgroup in algebra was discussed in [23]. More development about fuzzy subgroup may be viewed

in [24]. Shafei et al [25] studied the fuzzy logic control systems for demand management in airports and energy efficiency by using 3D simulator.

This paper is organized as the section 2 contains the elementary definition of Q -fuzzy subrings and related results which are thoroughly crucial to understand the novelty of this article. In section 3, we define the ω - Q -fuzzy subring and prove that the level subset of ω - Q -fuzzy subrings is a subring. We also define ω - Q -fuzzy ideal and discuss its properties. In section 5, we use the classical ring homomorphism to investigate the behavior of homomorphic image (inverse-image) of ω - Q -fuzzy subring.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We recall first the elementary notion of fuzzy sets which play a key role for our further analysis.

Definition 2.1. [1]: A fuzzy set A of a nonempty set M is a function,

$$A : P \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

Definition 2.2. [10]: Let A be fuzzy subset of a ring R . Then A is said to a fuzzy subring if

- i. $A(u - v) \geq \min\{A(u), A(v)\}$
- ii. $A(uv) \geq \min\{A(u), A(v)\}$, for all $u, v \in R$.

Definition 2.3. [14]: Let M and Q be two nonempty sets. A Q -fuzzy subset A of set M is a function $A: X \times Q \rightarrow [0,1]$ for all $u, v \in M$ and $q \in Q$.

Definition 2.4. [14]: A function $A : R \times Q \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a QFSRR of a ring R if

- i. $A(u - v, q) \geq \min\{A(u, q), A(v, q)\}$
- ii. $A(uv, q) \geq \min\{A(u, q), A(v, q)\}$, for all $u, v \in R$ and $q \in Q$.

Definition 2.5. Let the mapping $f: R_1 \rightarrow R_2$ be a homomorphism. Let A and B be ω -QFSRs of R_1 and R_2 respectively, then $f(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are image of A and the inverse image of B respectively, defined as

- i. $f(A)(v, q) = \begin{cases} \sup\{A(u, q) : u \in f^{-1}(v)\}, & \text{if } f^{-1}(v) \neq \emptyset \\ 0, & \text{if } f^{-1}(v) = \emptyset \end{cases}$, for every $v \in R_2$ and $q \in Q$
- ii. $f^{-1}(B)(u, q) = B(f(u), q)$, for every $u \in R_1$ and $q \in Q$

Definition 2.6. [13]: Let $t_p: [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ be the algebraic product t -norm on $[0,1]$ and is described as $t_p\{a, b\} = ab, 0 \leq a \leq 1, 0 \leq b \leq 1$

3. PROPERTIES OF ω - Q -FUZZY SUBRINGS

Definition 3.1. Let M and Q be any two nonempty sets and A be a Q -fuzzy subset of a set P , any $\omega \in [0,1]$. Then fuzzy set A^ω of M is said to be ω - Q -fuzzy subset of M (w.r.t Q -fuzzy set A) and defined by:

$$A^\omega(m, q) = t_p\{A(m, q), \omega\}, \text{ for all } m \in M \text{ and } q \in Q$$

Remark 3.2. Clearly, $A^1(m, q) = A(m, q)$ and $A^0(m, q) = 0$.

Remark 3.3. If A and B be two Q -fuzzy sets of M . Then $(A \cap B)^\omega = A^\omega \cap B^\omega$.

Definition 3.4. A Q -fuzzy subset of a ring R is called ω -QFSR, and $\omega \in [0,1]$, if

- i $A^\omega(m - n, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$, for all $m, n \in R$ and $q \in Q$.

Theorem 3.5. If A is a ω -QFSR of a ring R , then

$$A^\omega(m, q) \leq A^\omega(0, q), \text{ for all } m \in R \text{ and } q \in Q \text{ where } 0 \text{ is the additive identity of } R.$$

Proof: Consider $A^\omega(0, q) = A^\omega(m - m, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(m^{-1}, q)\}$

$$= \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(m, q)\} = A^\omega(m, q)$$

Hence, $A^\omega(0, q) \geq A^\omega(m, q)$, for all $m \in R$

Theorem 3.6. If A is QFSR of a ring R , then A is an ω -QFSR of R .

Proof: Assume that A is a QFSR of a ring R and $\forall a, b \in R$ and $q \in Q$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Assume that, } A^\omega(a-b, q) = t_p\{A(a-b, q), \mu\} \geq t_p\{\min\{A(a, q), A(b, q)\}, \omega\} \\
& = \min\{t_p\{A(a, q), \omega\}, t_p\{A(b, q), \omega\}\} = \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\} \\
& A^\omega(a-b, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\} \\
& \text{Further } A^\omega(ab, q) = t_p\{A(ab, q), \mu\} \geq t_p\{\min\{A(a, q), A(b, q)\}, \omega\} \\
& = \min\{t_p\{A(a, q), \omega\}, t_p\{A(b, q), \omega\}\} = \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\} \\
& \qquad \qquad \qquad A^\omega(ab, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, A is ω -QFSR of R . In general, the converse may not be true.

Note 3.7. we take $Q = \{q\}$ in all the examples

Example 3.8 Let $R = \{0,1,2,3\}$, be a ring and $Q = \{q\}$. Let the Q -fuzzy set A of R described by:

$$A(a, q) = \begin{cases} 0.3, & \text{if } a = 0 \\ 0.5, & \text{if } a = 1 \text{ or } 3 \\ 0.4, & \text{if } a = 2 \end{cases}$$

Take $\omega = 0$ then,

$$\begin{aligned}
A^\omega(a, q) &= t_p\{A(a, q), \omega\} = t_p\{A(a, q), 0\} = 0, \text{ for all } a \in R \\
&\Rightarrow A^\omega(a-b, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Further, we have $A^\omega(ab, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(a, q), A^\omega(b, q)\}$

Consequently A is ω -QFSR of R and A is not QFSR of R .

Definition 3.9. Let A be ω - Q -fuzzy set of universe set M . For $t, \omega \in [0,1]$ the level subset A_t^ω of ω - Q -fuzzy set is given by:

$$A_t^\omega = \{m \in M : A^\omega(m, q) \geq t\}$$

Theorem 3.10. Let A is ω - Q -fuzzy subring of R then A_t^ω is subring of R for all $t \leq A(0, q)$.

Proof: It is quite obvious that A^ω is non-empty. Since A be ω - Q -fuzzy subring of a ring R , which implies that $A^\omega(m, q) \leq A^\omega(0, q)$, for all $m \in R$ and $q \in Q$. Let $m, n \in A_t^\omega$ then $A^\omega(m, q) \geq t$ $A^\omega(n, q) \geq t$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
A^\omega(m-n, q) &\geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t \\
A^\omega(mn, q) &\geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t
\end{aligned}$$

This implies that $-n, mn \in A_t^\omega$. Hence, A_t^ω is subring of R .

Definition 3.11. Let A be a Q -fuzzy subset of a ring R and $\omega \in [0,1]$. Then A^ω is ω - Q -fuzzy left ideal (ω -QFLI) of R if,

- i $A^\omega(m-n, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$
- ii $A^\omega(mn, q) \geq A^\omega(n, q)$, for all $m, n \in R$ and $q \in Q$

Definition 3.12. Let A be a Q -fuzzy subset of a ring R and $\omega \in [0,1]$. Then A^ω is ω - Q -fuzzy right ideal (ω -QFRI) of R if,

- i. $A^\omega(m-n, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$
- ii. $A^\omega(mn, q) \geq A^\omega(m, q)$, for all $m, n \in R$ and $q \in Q$

Definition 3.13. Let A be a Q -fuzzy subset of a ring R and $\omega \in [0,1]$. Then A^ω is ω -QFI of R if,

- i. $A^\omega(m-n, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$
- ii. $A^\omega(mn, q) \geq \max\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$, for all $m, n \in R$ and $q \in Q$

Definition 3.14. Let A be a ω -QFSR of a ring R and $\omega \in [0,1]$. For any $m \in R$ and $q \in Q$. The ω - Q -fuzzy coset of A in R is represented by $m + A^\omega$ as defined as,

$(m + A^\omega)(h, q) = t_p\{A(h - m, q), \omega\} = A^\omega(h - m)$, for all $m, h \in R$ and $q \in Q$

Theorem 3.15. Let A be ω -QFI of ring R . Then the set

$A_0^\omega = \{m \in R : A^\omega(m, q) = A^\omega(0, q)\}$ is an ideal of ring R .

Proof: Obviously $A_0^\omega \neq \emptyset$ because $0 \in R$. Let $m, n \in A_0^\omega$ be any elements.

Consider

$$A^\omega(m - n, q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\} = \min\{A^\omega(0, q), A^\omega(0, q)\}$$

Implies that $A^\omega(m - n, q) \geq A^\omega(0, q)$. But $A^\omega(m - n, q) \leq A^\omega(0, q)$

Therefore, $A^\omega(m - n, q) = A^\omega(0, q)$

Implies that $m - n \in A_0^\omega$.

Further, let $m \in A_0^\omega$ and $n \in R$. Consider

$$A^\omega(mn, q) \geq \max\{A^\omega(m, q), A^\omega(n, q)\} = \max\{A^\omega(0, q), A^\omega(n, q)\}$$

Implies that $A^\omega(mn, q) \geq A^\omega(0, q)$. But $A^\omega(mn, q) \leq A^\omega(0, q)$

Therefore, $A^\omega(mn, q) = A^\omega(0, q)$.

Similarly, $A^\omega(nm, q) = A^\omega(0, q)$

Implies that $mn, nm \in A_0^\omega$.

Implies that A_0^ω is an ideal.

Theorem 3.16. Let A_0^ω be an ω -QFI of ring R , $m, n \in R$ and $q \in Q$. Then,

$$m + A^\omega = n + A^\omega \text{ if and if only } m - n \in A_0^\omega.$$

Proof: For any $m, n \in S$, we have $m + A^\omega = n + A^\omega$.

Consider,

$$A^\omega(m - n, q) = (n + A^\omega)(m, q) = (m + A^\omega)(m, q) = A^\omega(0, q)$$

Therefore, $m - n \in A_0^\omega$.

Conversely, let $m - n \in A_0^\omega$

Implies that $A^\omega(m - n, q) = A^\omega(0, q)$

Consider, $(m + A^\omega)(h, q) = A^\omega(h - m, q) = A^\omega((h - n) - (m - n), q)$

$$\geq \min\{A^\omega((h - n), q), A^\omega((m - n), q)\}$$

$$= \min\{A^\omega((h - n), q), A^\omega(0, q)\} = A^\omega((h - n), q) = (n + A^\omega)(h, q)$$

Interchange the role of p and q we get $(n + A^\omega)(h, q) \geq (m + A^\omega)(h, q)$

Therefore, $(m + A^\omega)(h, q) = (n + A^\omega)(h, q)$, for all $h \in R$

Definition 3.17. Let A be a ω -QFI of a ring R . The set of all ω -Q-fuzzy cosets of A denoted by R/A^ω form a ring with respect to binary operation $*$ defined by

$$(m + A^\omega) + (n + A^\omega) = (m + n) + A^\omega, \text{ where } m + A^\omega, n + A^\omega \in R/A^\omega, m, n \in R.$$

$(m + A^\omega) * (n + A^\omega) = (m * n) + A^\omega$, where $m + A^\omega, n + A^\omega \in R/A^\omega, m, n \in R$. The ring R/A^ω is called the factor ring of R with respect to ω -QFI A^ω .

Theorem 3.18. The set R/A^ω forms a ring with respect to the above stated binary operation.

Proof: Let $m_1 + A^\omega = m_2 + A^\omega$ and $n_1 + A^\omega = n_2 + A^\omega$ for some $m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in R$. Let $g \in R$ be any element of R and $q \in Q$.

$$\begin{aligned} (m_2 + n_2 + A^\omega)(g, q) &= A^\omega(g - (m_2 + n_2), q) \\ &= A^\omega((g - m_2 - n_2), q) = n_2 + A^\omega((g - m_2), q) = n_1 + A^\omega((g - m_2), q) \\ &= A^\omega((g - m_2 - n_1), q) = m_2 + A^\omega((g - n_1), q) = m_1 + A^\omega((g - n_1), q) \\ &= A^\omega((g - m_1 - n_1), q) = A^\omega(g - (m_1 + n_1), q) = (m_1 + n_1 + A^\omega)(g, q) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover,

$$(m_2 n_2 + A^\omega)(g, q) = A^\omega(g - m_1 n_1 - (m_2 n_2 - m_1 n_1), q)$$

$$\geq \min\{A^\omega(g - m_1n_1), A^\omega((m_2n_2 - m_1n_1), q)\}$$

But we have, $A^\omega((m_2n_2 - m_1n_1), q) = A^\omega((m_1n_1 - m_2n_1 + m_2n_1 - m_2n_2), q)$

$$= A^\omega((m_1 - m_2)n_1 + m_2(n_1 - n_2), q) \geq \min\{A^\omega(m_1 - m_2)n_1, q), A^\omega(m_2(n_1 - n_2), q)\}$$

$$= \min\{A^\omega((m_1 - m_2), q), A^\omega((n_1 - n_2), q)\}$$

$$= \min\{A^\omega(0, q), A^\omega(0, q)\}$$

$$A^\omega((m_2n_2 - m_1n_1), q) \geq A^\omega(0, q)$$

$$(m_2n_2 + A^\omega)(g, q) \geq A^\omega(g - m_1n_1), q)$$

$$= (m_1n_1 + A^\omega)(g, q)$$

Similarly, we can prove that $(m_2n_2 + A^\omega)(g, q) \leq (m_1n_1 + A^\omega)(g, q)$

Consequently, $(m_2n_2 + A^\omega)(g, q) = (m_1n_1 + A^\omega)(g, q)$.

Therefore $*$ is well defined. Now we prove that the following axioms of ring, for any $m, n \in R$.

- 1) $(m + A^\omega) + (n + A^\omega) = m + n + A^\omega$
- 2) $(m + A^\omega) + [(n + A^\omega) + (r + A^\omega)] = m + A^\omega + [n + r + A^\omega] = (m + n) + r + A^\omega = [m + n + A^\omega] + r + A^\omega = [(m + A^\omega) + (n + A^\omega)] + (r + A^\omega)$
- 3) $(m + A^\omega) + (n + A^\omega) = m + n + A^\omega = n + m + A^\omega = (n + A^\omega) + (m + A^\omega)$
- 4) $(0 + A^\omega) + (n + A^\omega) = (n + A^\omega)$
- 5) $(m + A^\omega) + (-m + A^\omega) = A^\omega$
- 6) $(m + A^\omega)(n + A^\omega) = mn + A^\omega$
- 7) $(m + A^\omega)[(n + A^\omega)(r + A^\omega)] = m + A^\omega + [nr + A^\omega] = mnr + A^\omega = [mn + A^\omega] + r + A^\omega = [(m + A^\omega)(n + A^\omega)](r + A^\omega)$
- 8) $(m + A^\omega)[(n + A^\omega) + (r + A^\omega)] = (m + A^\omega)[(n + r) + A^\omega] = m(n + r) + A^\omega = (mn + mr) + A^\omega = (mn + A^\omega) + (mr + A^\omega) = [(m + A^\omega)(n + A^\omega) + (m + A^\omega)(r + A^\omega)]$
- 9) $[(n + A^\omega) + (r + A^\omega)](m + A^\omega) = [(n + r) + A^\omega](m + A^\omega) = (n + r)m + A^\omega = (nm + rm) + A^\omega = (nm + A^\omega) + (rm + A^\omega) = [(n + A^\omega)(m + A^\omega) + (r + A^\omega)(m + A^\omega)]$

Consequently, $(R/A^\omega, +, *)$ is a ring.

4. HOMOMORPHISM OF ω -Q-FUZZY SUBRINGS

In this section, we investigate the behavior of homomorphic image and inverse image of ω -QFSR.

Lemma 4.1. Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be a mapping and A and B be two fuzzy subsets of M and N respectively, then

- i. $f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m, q) = (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m, q)$, for all $m \in M$ and $q \in Q$
- ii. $f(A^\omega)(n, q) = (f(A))^\omega(n, q)$, for all $n \in N$ and $q \in Q$

Proof:

$$(i) f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m) = B^\omega(f(m)) = t_p\{B(f(m)), \omega\} = t_p\{f^{-1}(B)(m), \omega\}$$

$$f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m) = (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m), \text{ for all } m \in M$$

$$(ii) f(A^\omega)(n, q) = \sup\{A^\omega(m, q): f(m) = y\} = \sup\{t_p\{A(m, q), \omega\}: f(m) = n\}$$

$$= t_p\{\sup\{A(m, q): f(m) = n\}, \omega\} = t_p\{f(A)(n, q), \omega\} = (f(A))^\omega(n, q), \text{ for all } n \in N$$

$$\text{Hence, } f(A^\omega)(n, q) = (f(A))^\omega(n, q)$$

Theorem 4.2. Let $f: R_1 \rightarrow R_2$ be a homomorphism from a ring R_1 to a ring R_2 and A be a ω -QFSR of ring R_1 . Then $f(A)$ is a ω -QFSR of ring R_2 .

Proof: Let A be a ω -QFSR of ring R_1 . Let $n_1, n_2 \in R_2$ be any element. Then there exists unique elements $m_1, m_2 \in R_1$ such that $f(m_1) = n_1$ and $f(m_2) = n_2$ and for $q \in Q$.

Consider,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (f(A))^\omega(n_1 - n_2, q) &= t_p\{f(A)(n_1 - n_2, q), \omega\} = t_p\{f(A)(f(m_1) - f(m_2), q), \omega\} \\
 &= t_p\{f(A)(f(m_1 - m_2), q), \omega\} = t_p\{A(m_1 - m_2, q), \omega\} = A^\omega(m_1 - m_2, q) \\
 &\geq \min\{A^\omega(m_1, q), A^\omega(m_2, q)\}, \text{ for all } m_1, m_2 \in H_1 \text{ such that } f(m_1) = n_1 \text{ and } f(m_2) = n_2\} \\
 &\geq \min\{\sup\{A^\omega(m_1, q) : f(m_1) = n_1\}, \sup\{A^\omega(m_2, q) : f(m_2) = n_2\}\} \\
 &= \min\{f(A^\omega)(n_1, q), f(A^\omega)(n_2, q)\} = \min\{(f(A))^\omega(n_1, q), (f(A))^\omega(n_2, q)\} \\
 \text{Thus, } (f(A))^\omega(n_1 n_2, q) &\geq \min\{(f(A))^\omega(n_1, q), (f(A))^\omega(n_2, q)\} \\
 \text{Further, } (f(A))^\omega(n_1 n_2, q) &= t_p\{f(A)(n_1 n_2, q), \omega\} = t_p\{f(A)(f(m_1)f(m_2), q), \omega\} \\
 &= t_p\{f(A)(f(m_1 m_2), q), \omega\} = t_p\{A(m_1 m_2, q), \omega\} = A^\omega(m_1 m_2, q) \\
 &\geq \min\{A^\omega(m_1, q), A^\omega(m_2, q)\}, \text{ for all } m_1, m_2 \in H_1 \text{ such that } f(m_1) = n_1 \text{ and } f(m_2) = n_2\} \\
 &\geq \min\{\sup\{A^\omega(m_1, q) : f(m_1) = n_1\}, \sup\{A^\omega(m_2, q) : f(m_2) = n_2\}\} \\
 &= \min\{f(A^\omega)(n_1, q), f(A^\omega)(n_2, q)\} = \min\{(f(A))^\omega(n_1, q), (f(A))^\omega(n_2, q)\} \\
 \text{Thus, } (f(A))^\omega(n_1 n_2, q) &\geq \min\{(f(A))^\omega(n_1, q), (f(A))^\omega(n_2, q)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $f(A)$ is ω -QFSR of R_2 .

Theorem 4.3. Let $f : R_1 \rightarrow R_2$ be a homomorphism from ring R_1 into a ring R_2 and B be a ω -QFSR of ring R_2 . Then $f^{-1}(B)$ is ω -QFSR of ring R_1 .

Proof: Let B be ω -QFSR of ring R_2 . Let $m_1, m_2 \in R_1$ be any elements, then $(f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1 - m_2, q) = f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_1 - m_2, q) = B^\omega(f(m_1 - m_2), q)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= B^\omega(f(m_1) - f(m_2), q) \\
 &\geq \min\{B^\omega(f(m_1), q), B^\omega(f(m_2), q)\} = \min\{f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_1, q), f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_2, q)\} \\
 &= \min\{(f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1, q), (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_2, q)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Thus, } (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1 m_2, q) &\geq \min\{(f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1, q), (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_2, q)\} \\
 \text{Further, } (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1 m_2, q) &= f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_1 m_2, q) = B^\omega(f(m_1 m_2), q) = B^\omega(f(m_1)f(m_2), q) \\
 &\geq \min\{B^\omega(f(m_1), q), B^\omega(f(m_2), q)\} = \min\{f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_1, q), f^{-1}(B^\omega)(m_2, q)\} \\
 &= \min\{(f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1, q), (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_2, q)\} \\
 \text{Thus, } (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1 m_2, q) &\geq \min\{(f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_1, q), (f^{-1}(B))^\omega(m_2, q)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $f^{-1}(B)$ is ω -QFSR of a ring R_1 .

5. CONCLUSION

In paper, we have proved the level subset of two ω -Q-fuzzy subrings is a subring. In addition, we have extended the study of this ideology to investigate the effect of image and inverse image of ω -QFSR under ring homomorphism.

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Conflict of interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest in this paper

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